

Towards Real-Time Safe UAV Trajectory Planning Using Clustering of Nearby UAVs in Dense Urban Environments

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Abstract—Rapid urbanization trends have resulted in a significant increase in global urban population over the past few decades. This growth is projected to continue, further exacerbating traffic congestion in road networks. Urban air mobility presents a promising solution to alleviate this congestion, offering substantial environmental, economic, and societal benefits. However, to fully realize these benefits, autonomous flight and automation are crucial for safely managing the high density of aircraft expected in urban airspaces.

To address this challenge, this work proposes an innovative model predictive control (MPC) framework for generating on-demand, safe 3D trajectories for fleets of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) operating in dense urban environments. Specifically, it introduces a near real-time MPC method designed to enhance the airspace’s capacity to accommodate an increasing number of flights within a confined area, while consistently adhering to stringent safety standards. An extensive simulation study is conducted to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed framework in planning safe, on-demand trajectories in complex urban settings.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the recent years, increased urbanization has significantly escalated the traffic congestion problem in urban areas, leading to increased environmental pollution, economic losses, and a reduced quality of life [1]. Urban air mobility (UAM) has been identified as a potential solution to this problem, as it aims to provide efficient and sustainable transportation solutions, focusing on the use of primarily autonomous aircrafts to transport passengers and cargo within urban or densely populated areas. UAM encompasses various applications, including air taxis, delivery drones, and cargo flights, all of which use advanced technologies and autonomous systems to operate safely and efficiently in urban environments [2]. In particular, the development of vertically operated electric take-off and landing (eVTOL) aircraft has brought significant improvements in safety and noise reduction compared to conventional aircraft, making UAM a more commercially viable and environmentally friendly option. As a result, UAM is increasingly becoming a reality, and pilot projects and partnerships have already been established in various regions of the world [3].

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However, UAM’s implementation poses formidable challenges beyond the capabilities of current air traffic management (ATM) systems. In general, UAM flights operate within close proximity over densely populated regions, with flights traversing unconventional altitudes and lacking fixed routes. Thus, new and innovative approaches to ATM are needed to ensure that UAM can operate safely and efficiently in urban environments. In recent years, relevant authorities began investigating different aspects of the UAM problem [4], including the development of a safe and efficient ATM system for UAM, where passenger-carrying air taxis can operate above populated areas.

Hence, substantial research efforts have been dedicated to UAM, aiming to attain a robust flying infrastructure capable of effectively managing unanticipated or unpredictable situations without detrimentally impacting the system’s overall performance [5]–[7]. Nevertheless, current works do not provide a safety guarantee on selected trajectories, as instances of loss of separation (LOS), denoting a breach in the intended safety margins between UAVs, have been observed in simulations carried out within densely flying environments [8], [9]. In addition, current ATM systems are primarily designed for low-density airspaces and do not adequately address the challenges posed by scaled-up deployments [10]–[13]. However, as UAM envisions the integration of large vehicles and a significant increase in traffic density, it becomes imperative to explore and develop a safe and sustainable solution to UAM air traffic management.

The primary aim of this work is to investigate a 3D trajectory planning system that addresses the scalability issues by accomplishing three key objectives: (i) ensuring a guaranteed separation between UAVs to minimize the risk of collisions; (ii) efficiently managing the anticipated surge in traffic density without inefficiently utilizing airspace capacity to mitigate LOS occurrences; and (iii) providing real-time response in computing routes, enabling rapid adaptation to dynamically evolving operational conditions. Specifically, the contributions of this work are as follows:

- the dynamic planning of safe flight paths by modeling the present and anticipated uncertainties in UAV locations. This on-line approach ensures guaranteed bounds on LOS probability between UAVs.
- the design of a framework that generates artificial segregated airspace by clustering UAVs in close proximity to form exclusion zones and in doing so also minimizes computational complexity of new trajectories.
- the design of a framework that effectively mitigates “congested” portions of airspace, thereby enhancing flow efficiency under dynamic operational conditions.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section II presents the current state-of-the-art on UAM techniques, Section III offers a detailed description of the UAV dynamical model, and Section IV presents the design and application specifics of the proposed UAV coordination framework, elaborating on the problem formulation designed to compute guaranteed safe trajectories with minimum flight times, the clustering of UAVs, and a UAV decongestion scheme. Section V evaluates the proposed framework through extensive testing, and Section VI concludes the work and outlines avenues for future research.

II. RELATED WORK

Autonomous UAM involves determining safe trajectories for aircraft sharing the airspace, effectively avoiding static obstacles and other aircraft. A widely used method entails computing convex decompositions of the free space by constructing minimal-volume outer polyhedral representations of existing obstacles. Trajectory planning is then constrained to remain within these convex regions. The authors in [14] suggest an approach that makes the volumes of outer polyhedral representations for trajectories smaller compared to those achieved using traditional Bernstein and B-Spline bases. To ensure non-conservative constraints for collision avoidance with other obstacles and agents, the proposed approach incorporates decision variables that define separating planes for each pair of outer polyhedral representations. Nevertheless, that method fails to consider the presence of uncertainty during the execution of the planned trajectory by each UAV.

Further, the work in [15] proposes a systematic approach to address the robust multi-drone planning challenge at high speeds. This approach incorporates a space-time capsule constraint, which aims to ensure mutual safety even when a drone deviates significantly from the predefined flight plan. While the suggested framework offers a solution for robust trajectory planning, it does not consider uncertainty factors or provide a provision for a bounded probability of collision. Moreover, in [16], the authors propose a solution specifically adapted for fixed-wing UAVs. Their work employs the Dubins method, with its limitations in handling symmetrical scenarios addressed through a more collaborative approach, known as the shunted strategy. Specifically, the Dubins path becomes infeasible when UAVs approach their near-goal positions and encounter other UAVs, often leading to a standstill. Although the experimental results indicate the effectiveness and practical potential of this method, it appears to be primarily geared to fixed-wing UAVs, which are subject to more pronounced movement constraints. Furthermore, the simulation experiments are performed at relatively low speeds and do not incorporate the effects of location uncertainty.

For more realistic UAV motion models, in [17] an approach utilizing stochastic optimal control is proposed to generate conflict-free 3D trajectories, considering the uncertainties associated with flight. The method incorporates a probabilistic collision detection framework, which employs a generalized polynomial chaos method. To solve the resulting nonlinear programming problem, sequential quadratic programming is employed. In another recent study presented in

[18], a chance-constraint nonlinear model predictive control (MPC) problem is introduced for the distributed generation of collision-free trajectories for multiple UAVs. The objective is to minimize the controls for individual UAVs. Additionally, a distributed MPC-based approach for multi-robot motion planning is described in [19], in order to minimize the UAVs' energy consumption. Furthermore, our previous work in [20] demonstrates cooperative solutions aimed at minimizing flight time within a network of interconnected UAVs. However, these aforementioned solutions lack techniques to effectively address the challenges associated with scaling these methods to accommodate large and densely populated flying environments. Moreover, several works introduce the incorporation of a potential field cost to enforce adherence to a safe distance between UAVs, when deemed necessary [17]–[19]. Nevertheless, in the context of UAM, these works are not directly applicable, as they do not consider higher-speed larger UAVs, long-distance flights, etc.

In addition to the advancements detailed above, the work in [21] introduces an MPC technique integrating a collision avoidance cost function to generate trajectories free of collisions, albeit limited to a 2D implementation. Furthermore, in [22], the issue of devising secure trajectories for multiple agents, considering collision avoidance constraints, is framed as a sequential decision-making problem resolved through deep reinforcement learning. However, it is important to note that the evaluation of this methodology is exclusively conducted within restricted spatial confines and focuses solely on terrestrial robotic systems.

Contrary to the aforementioned studies, this work focuses on the need for a distributed coordination framework with the flexibility to (re)optimize 3D trajectories in an online fashion. The proposed approach is designed to scale effectively with changing UAV fleet sizes while accounting for low-level dynamics and associated model uncertainties to ensure safe UAV routes.

III. UAV DYNAMICS

In this work, the underlying assumption is that a given set \mathcal{M} of UAVs possesses the capability to establish intercommunication, exchange relevant data, and effectively navigate within a 3D environment. The motion model employed for the UAVs is based on discrete-time linear dynamics [19], [20]:

$$\mathbf{x}_t^j = \Phi \mathbf{x}_{t-1}^j + \Gamma \mathbf{f}_{t-1}^j + \mathbf{G} \sigma_{t-1}^j, \quad j \in [1, \dots, |\mathcal{M}|]. \quad (1)$$

The state of the j -th UAV at time t is indicated by \mathbf{x}_t^j , which is a 6-dimensional vector in \mathbb{R}^6 . It consists of the position and velocity components of the UAV in 3D Cartesian coordinates. The position is represented by a 3-dimensional vector $[p_x, p_y, p_z]_t^j$, while the velocity is represented by a 3-dimensional vector $[\nu_x, \nu_y, \nu_z]_t^j$. To control the UAV, a force vector \mathbf{f}_t^j is applied to it at time t . The force vector is a 3-dimensional vector $[f_x^j, f_y^j, f_z^j]_t^j$ in \mathbb{R}^3 . The UAV's motion model is subject to noise, which can be caused by factors like wind or external forces. This noise is represented by σ_t^j , which is a 3-dimensional vector $[\sigma_x^j, \sigma_y^j, \sigma_z^j]_t^j$ drawn from a multivariate normal distribution with zero mean and diagonal covariance matrix Σ_σ^j [23]. Given the linear

dynamics adopted by the UAV, the matrices Φ , Γ and \mathbf{G} are further given by:

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_3 & \delta T \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & \phi \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix}, \Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_3 \\ \gamma \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5\delta T^2 \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \delta T \cdot \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

with δT denoting the sampling interval, and \mathbf{I}_3 and $\mathbf{0}_3$ being the identity and zero matrices of dimension 3×3 , respectively. The parameters ϕ and γ are given by $\phi = (1-\eta)$ and $\gamma = \frac{\delta T}{m^j}$, where η is used to model the resistance to air and m^j represents the mass of the j^{th} UAV. The dynamics of the UAVs, as outlined in Eq. (1), adhere to the Markov property. Given an initial state denoted by \mathbf{x}_0 and a series of control inputs $\mathbf{f}_{0:CH-1}$ extending over CH time-steps (where CH is the length of the control horizon), the recursive computation of the UAV's state, \mathbf{x}_t , $t \in [1, \dots, CH]$, can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \Phi^t \mathbf{x}_0 + \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \Phi^\tau [\Gamma \mathbf{f}_{t-\tau-1} + \mathbf{G} \sigma_{t-\tau-1}], \quad \forall t, \quad (3)$$

where, for clarity, index j of the UAV is excluded. Subsequently, the UAV path $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_t\}, t \in [1, \dots, CH]$ over CH is a stochastic process, where each future state \mathbf{x}_t is distributed according to $\mathbf{x}_t \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_t, \Psi_t)$ with $\mu_t = [\boldsymbol{\mu}, \dot{\boldsymbol{\mu}}]_t^\top$ and Ψ_t given by [24]:

$$\mu_t = \Phi^t \mathbf{x}_0 + \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \Phi^\tau \Gamma \mathbf{f}_{t-\tau-1}, \quad \Psi_t = \sum_{\tau=0}^{t-1} \Phi^\tau \mathbf{Q} (\Phi^\tau)^\top, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{G} \Sigma_\sigma \mathbf{G}^\top$ is the covariance of the Gaussian disturbance in one step that acts on the system. The forces applied, denoted as $\mathbf{f}_{0:CH-1}$, do not impact the covariance matrix Ψ_t , allowing for its computation in advance. Consequently, when calculating forces for a UAV, the focus lies on modifying the μ_t of the predicted state, rather than altering its distribution.

IV. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

The problem formulation presented in this section aims to compute UAV trajectories that are both LOS-free and time-efficient. The underlying optimization framework incorporates uncertainty propagation, which is approximated using piecewise linear constraints, as described in [20] and briefly summarized in Section IV-A. While this approach provides an optimal solution to the trajectory planning problem, it incurs significant computational complexity. To address this, Sections IV-B and IV-C propose clustering-based strategies that encapsulate groups of UAVs within a simplex or a cuboid, respectively, thereby reducing computational burden and indirectly mitigating traffic congestion. Additionally, Section IV-D introduces a penalty mechanism (referred to as the *Clutter Decongestion Penalty*) designed to directly address congestion in densely occupied regions of the airspace.

A. The Motion Control-Slack Variables (MC-SV) approach

This section describes how UAV paths are obtained by optimizing the applied forces, as presented in [20]. The process follows a receding horizon distributed approach, where at each time step, UAV j , indexed within a predefined sorted

list, receives the planned trajectories of all preceding UAVs in the list, i.e., UAVs $\{1, \dots, j-1\}$. Based on this information, UAV j computes its own control inputs to generate an optimal and LOS-free trajectory for the future time steps. Slack variables λ are incorporated to enable the framework to overcome possible infeasibilities, by attenuating the safety constraints to the level necessary to attain functionality. In the general formulation presented below, $i \in \mathcal{F}_j$ refers to any UAV acting as a dynamic obstacle for UAV j :

Problem Motion Control-Slack Variables (MC-SV):

$$\min_{\mathbf{f}_{[0:CH-1]}} \sum_{t=1}^{CH} \|\mu_t^j - \mathbf{P}^j\| + w \sum_{t=1}^{CH} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{F}_j} \lambda_t^{i,j} \quad (5a)$$

subject to:

$$|\mathbf{f}_t^j| \leq f_{MAX} \quad \forall t \quad (5b)$$

$$|\mathbf{f}_t^j - \mathbf{f}_{t-1}^j| \leq \Delta f \quad \forall t \quad (5c)$$

$$|\dot{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_t^j| \leq v_{MAX} \quad \forall t \quad (5d)$$

$$\mathbf{A}_t^{i,j} (\mu_t^j - \mu_t^i) + \lambda_t^{i,j} \leq \mathbf{c}_t^{i,j} + \mathbf{b}_t^{i,j} M, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F}_j, \forall t \leq SH \quad (5e)$$

$$b_t^{i,j}(p) \in \{0, 1\}, b_t^{i,j}(p) \in b_t^{i,j}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F}_j, \forall t \leq SH \quad (5f)$$

$$\sum_{p=1}^{\kappa} b_t^{i,j}(p) < \kappa, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{F}_j, \forall t \leq SH \quad (5g)$$

$$0 \leq \lambda_t^{i,j}, \quad \forall t \quad (5h)$$

In the MC-SV problem formulation, the objective function is defined in Eq. (5a). The first term represents the cumulative expected distance between the ego UAV and its destination \mathbf{P}^j over the next future CH time steps, where the expected positions μ are given by Eq. (4). The second term penalizes the use of slack variables through a weighted summation, where the weight w is set to a high value to discourage reliance on these variables. To promote realistic control inputs, Constraint (5b) limits the magnitude of applied forces to f_{MAX} , while Constraint (5c) restricts the difference between consecutive control inputs to a maximum of Δf .

Safety among UAVs sharing the same airspace is enforced by Constraints (5e)–(5g). Specifically, a minimum separation distance $d_{MIN}^{i,j}$ is maintained between the expected future positions of UAVs i and j . This is achieved by ensuring that the ellipsoids representing the uncertainty around each UAV's barycenter, derived from their Gaussian position distributions in Eq. (4), remain at least d_{MIN} apart. To make the resulting optimization problem convex, the constraint on the distance between the UAVs is conservatively approximated by polyhedra centered at the expected positions of each UAV $i \in \mathcal{F}_j$. The polyhedral constraints are encoded using matrix \mathbf{A} , whose rows contain the outward normal vectors of the polyhedron's κ faces, and vector \mathbf{c} , which contains the corresponding offset terms (i.e., the dot products of the normals with points lying on each face). Further technical details on this construction can be found in [20]. Slack variables are incorporated in Constraint (5e) to ensure constraint feasibility when strict enforcement of d_{MIN} is not possible. When activated (i.e., when they assume nonzero values), these variables adjust the corresponding planes, effectively relaxing the safety constraint. While this relaxation expands the

feasible region of the optimization problem and increases its robustness in challenging scenarios, it may compromise strict safety guarantees by allowing temporary LOS. Constraint (5h) ensures that all slack variables remain nonnegative, i.e., $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$. To reduce computational complexity, a safety horizon (*SH*) is employed, which limits the number of future steps for which safety constraints are evaluated, as discussed in [25].

B. Regular Tetrahedron Clustering Method

This section presents an approach that facilitates the discovery of UAVs that are flying in close proximity, and groups them together, firstly reducing the complexity of the method, and secondly exploiting the fact that since multiple UAVs are near each other, the ego UAV LOS avoidance constraint excludes trajectories maneuvering through the gap between the group of UAVs. Thus, in this case a group of closely-spaced UAVs are not considered multiple obstacles but a single obstacle that the ego UAV has to avoid. For building the single obstacle, identification of the distinct closely-spaced UAVs is initially required; this is achieved through UAV clustering by using the constant distance between the expected locations of the UAVs μ and the size of the uncertainty sphere $|\Psi|$.

Specifically, UAV clusters are generated using the density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN) method [26]. DBSCAN groups together UAVs that are closely packed and marks as outliers those that lie alone in low-density regions. Additionally, DBSCAN does not require the number of clusters to be defined a priori. These two properties make the DBSCAN method fit for use for the problem at hand. In the DBSCAN algorithm, two critical parameters are defined: (i) ε - defines the radius of the neighborhood around a point. It is the maximum distance between two points so as to be considered neighbors; and (ii) MinPts - specifies the minimum number of points required within the ε -neighborhood for a point to be classified as a core point, thus forming a dense region or cluster.

In this way, MinPts will be equal to 1 for UAV locations that are considered outliers (in essence creating their own individual cluster). Parameter ε is set at $30m$; this takes into account the minimum constant safety distance between UAVs (set at $10m$) and the radius of each uncertainty sphere, that reaches a maximum length of approximately $13m$ by the end of the SH (including also an additional margin for error). By setting the parameters and implementing DBSCAN the aim is to exploit spatial information to reduce unnecessary complexity of the framework without compromising safety.

After clustering the UAVs, a polyhedron is used that encloses the uncertainty spheres of the locations. In this way, the chance constraint will still be respected, and therefore LOS avoidance will be enforced. The *regular tetrahedron* is chosen as the enclosing polyhedron. The polyhedron is selected as it allows the reduction of binary numbers within the optimization problem, while at the same time retaining a piecewise-linear optimization. Apart from combining the UAVs as a single entity under a *simplex* (note that in geometry, a simplex is a generalization of the notion of a triangle or tetrahedron to arbitrary dimensions), it is also essential

to employ a simplex that approaches the minimum possible volume in order to avoid overly conservative optimizations and to avoid unduly restricting the feasible region. This ensures that the optimization process remains efficient, while also accurately representing the solution space.

Constructing a pyramid to encapsulate clustered UAVs in 3D space presents a complex challenge, as it involves determining a bounding geometry for effectively enclosing the UAVs which has a volume that approaches the minimum. After clustering the UAVs based on the centroid \bar{c} of μ , a sphere is built with a radius r_{max} that is equal to the maximum distance between the centroid \bar{c} and any point \mathbf{p}_i on the surface of the sphere. The radius finally used is given by $r_{max} = \max \|\bar{c} - \mathbf{p}_i\|$. From geometry, it is given that the radius r_{max} of the inscribed sphere in a regular tetrahedron with edge length a is $r_{max} = a/\sqrt{24}$.

Based on the aforementioned description, a regular tetrahedron is constructed that has an inscribed sphere with radius r_{max} and center the centroid \bar{c} . The tetrahedron created is overly conservative, thus in order to further minimize its volume the following procedure is followed: First a principal component analysis (PCA) is performed. The directions of the two eigenvectors with the two larger eigenvalues are exploited to tilt and rotate the tetrahedron. One of the points of the tetrahedron is aligned to the eigenvector (obtained by PCA) with the corresponding largest eigenvalue, while one of the other three vertices is rotated to be co-planar to the plane defined by the eigenvectors with the corresponding first and second largest eigenvalues. After the rotations of the tetrahedron, each of the tetrahedron planes is moved until it is tangent to its closest uncertainty sphere. It is noted that the planes' directions are kept the same. This procedure is repeated for all four planes. Then the new intersection points between the four planes will be the new vertices for the final tetrahedron considered, that will serve as the single obstacle the ego UAV will try to avoid (see Fig. 1).

In general, this method creates a Regular Rotated Tetrahedron (RRT) enclosing the UAVs with volume approaching the minimum by exploiting the aforementioned process. After constructing the tetrahedron, linear constraints are built based on it. The methodology keeps its 4D format as for each time-step different clusters are built. The optimization is still piecewise-linear but with reduced complexity. The methodology followed for constructing the tetrahedron is briefly explained in Alg.1.

When the regular tetrahedron clustering method is used (RRT), the new motion control optimization formulation, now called *RRT Motion Control (RRT-MC)*, keeps the objective function (Eq. (5a)) and Constraints (5b)-(5f) the same. The main difference is the polyhedron used; i.e., the aforementioned formulation uses the tetrahedron as the polyhedron to encapsulate uncertainty spheres, leading to $\kappa = 4$ in Constraint (5g) (i.e., the constraint enforcing that the UAV avoids the tetrahedron).

C. Bounding Box Clustering Method

The Bounding Box Clustering (BBC) method uses the DBSCAN approach as well, but instead of enclosing the UAVs into a simplex, it encloses them into a cuboid (note that

Fig. 1: (a) A cluster of two UAVs with their uncertainty spheres, (b) A sphere with radius r_{max} that encapsulates both UAVs (also illustrating the PCA eigenvectors), (c) Rotated tetrahedron with the inscribed sphere, and (d) Rotated tetrahedron with volume approaching the minimum, that encapsulates only the two uncertainty spheres of the cluster.

Algorithm 1 RRT

- 1: **Input:** Set of 3D points $\mathcal{P} = \{\mathbf{p}_1, \mathbf{p}_2, \dots, \mathbf{p}_n\}$
 - 2: **Output:** Rotated Regular Tetrahedron RRT
 - 3: Compute the centroid $\bar{\mathbf{c}}$ of \mathcal{P}
 - 4: PCA of \mathcal{P}
 - 5: Compute $r_{max} = \max \|\bar{\mathbf{c}} - \mathbf{p}_i\|$
 - 6: Construct sphere with radius r_{max} and center $\bar{\mathbf{c}}$
 - 7: Construct regular tetrahedron $\mathcal{RT} = \{\mathbf{tp}_1, \mathbf{tp}_2, \mathbf{tp}_3, \mathbf{tp}_4\}$ enclosing the sphere $(\bar{\mathbf{c}}, r_{max})$ with edge $a = \sqrt{24r_{max}^2}$
 - 8: Compute angle θ_1 required to align \mathbf{tp}_1
 - 9: Rotated position

$$\mathbf{tp}'_1 = \mathbf{tp}_1 \cos \theta_1 + (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{tp}_1) \sin \theta_1 + \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{tp}_1)(1 - \cos \theta_1)$$
 - 10: Compute angle θ_2 required to make \mathbf{tp}_2 coplanar
 - 11: Rotated position

$$\mathbf{tp}'_2 = \mathbf{tp}_2 \cos \theta_2 + (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{tp}_2) \sin \theta_2 + \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{tp}_2)(1 - \cos \theta_2)$$
 - 12: **for all** Surfaces $\mathcal{S} = \{\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \mathbf{s}_3, \mathbf{s}_4\}$ **do**
 - 13: $d_{move} = \min \|\mathbf{s}_j - \mathbf{p}_i\|$
 - 14: $\mathbf{s}'_j \leftarrow ax + by + cz + (D - d_{move} \|\mathbf{n}_i\|) = 0$
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: New vertices \mathbf{tp}''_i of tetrahedron are the intersections of all \mathbf{s}'_i pairs.
 - 17: **return** RRT
-

a cuboid is a hexahedron with quadrilateral faces, meaning it is a polyhedron with six faces; it has eight vertices and twelve edges). The cuboid ensures minimal volume bounding box that encloses the spheres, thus by using this method minimal encompassing space can be attained. The method to find minimal volume bounding box is based on Joseph O'Rourke's algorithm that computes minimal volume enclosing boxes [27] (presented in Alg. 2). It begins by computing the convex hull of the point set, simplifying the problem since the minimal bounding box of the point set is identical to that of its convex hull. The method proceeds with systematically rotating calipers in 3D around the convex hull to evaluate potential orientations of the bounding box. After the minimal volume bounding box is set, the framework proceeds with building the constraints based on its planes.

Algorithm 2 Compute Minimal-Volume Enclosing Box

- 1: **Input:** Set of 3D points $\mathcal{P} = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$
 - 2: **Output:** Minimal-volume enclosing box \mathbf{B}
 - 3: Compute the convex hull \mathbf{H} of \mathcal{P}
 - 4: Initialize $V_{min} \leftarrow \infty$
 - 5: **for all** triplets of orthogonal edges (e_1, e_2, e_3) of \mathbf{H} **do**
 - 6: Compute the orientation matrix \mathbf{M} defined by (e_1, e_2, e_3)
 - 7: Rotate \mathbf{H} using \mathbf{M} to align e_1, e_2, e_3 with coordinate axes
 - 8: Compute the bounding box \mathbf{B}' of the rotated \mathbf{H}
 - 9: Compute the volume V' of \mathbf{B}'
 - 10: **if** $V' < V_{min}$ **then**
 - 11: $V_{min} \leftarrow V'$
 - 12: $\mathbf{B} \leftarrow \mathbf{B}'$
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: **return** \mathbf{B}
-

When the BBC method is used for clustering, a new motion control optimization is formulated, called *Bounding Box Clustering-Motion Control (BBC-MC)*, that keeps the objective function (Eq. (5a)) and Constraints (5b)-(5g) the same. However, as a cuboid, rather than the tetrahedron, is now utilized as the polyhedron to encapsulate uncertainty spheres, this leads to $\kappa = 6$ in Constraint (5g) (i.e., the constraint enforcing that the UAV avoids the cuboid). It should be noted that if the cluster comprises of only one UAV then the tetrahedron, rather than a cuboid, is used to encapsulate the uncertainty sphere, leading to $\kappa = 4$ in Constraint (5g).

D. Negative Slacks Variables

As previously discussed in Section IV-A, LOS may not be avoided when computing routes for the UAVs. Introducing an increasing number of UAVs in a certain area, while considering the aforementioned methods, may limit the feasible trajectories. The implementation of negative slacks (i.e., $\lambda \in (-\infty, 0]$) is a technique that can be used to push UAVs to fly even further apart, while optimizing their paths to their respective destinations. In essence, when Constraint (5e) is active and the value of the slack variable is negative, it translates to pushing the right-hand-side of the constraint

to be larger, thereby enlarging the overall volume of the simplex/cuboid used. In that case, negative slack variables act as a repellent force to other UAVs, driving the UAVs to sparse locations, and thus resulting in reduced congestion and increased safety. Although this method seems similar to Artificial Potential Fields [28], its main difference lies in the linearity of the constraint. By implementing slack variables the constraint remains linear, maintaining a low complexity. Additionally, by adding the slack variables as control variables allows the optimization to set optimized values in order to arrive at the destination as soon as possible, while avoiding the rest of the UAVs. Hereafter, the proposed formulation with negative slacks is denoted as *Clutter Decongestion Penalty - Motion Control (CDP-MC)*.

The *CDP-MC* optimization formulation is the same as the previous formulations, with the only difference being the bounds on λ . Thus, Constraint (5h) is now transformed to $0 \leq -\lambda_t^{i,j}$, with the slack variables now belonging to \mathbb{R}_0^- . With this simple change the *CDP-MC* framework is expected to further decongest UAVs.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, an evaluation is conducted to assess the performance of the proposed formulations and also compare them against the state-of-the-art algorithm presented in [25]. A simplified scenario is introduced to showcase how the proposed frameworks respond to slack variables and their impact on the trajectories. The solution to all optimizations is derived using the GUROBI solver [29]. All simulations are executed through a time-slotted ad-hoc MatLab simulator on a computing platform having 4 CPUs and 16GB RAM.

A. Scenario Set-Up

A basic scenario is introduced to showcase both the functionality of the proposed framework and the utilization of the receding horizon strategy, clustering method, and the negative slack variables implementation. For this set-up $b = 100\text{m}$ (parameter for setting the starting points) and $|\mathcal{M}| = 6$ (i.e., 6 UAVs are used). Six total starting/landing points are selected; the initial configurations are distributed along the periphery of a theoretical circular boundary, with the starting/landing points being at

$$\begin{bmatrix} -b & 0 & 0 \\ b & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -b & 0 \\ 0 & b & 0 \\ \frac{-\sqrt{2b^2}}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{2b^2}}{2} & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

and with the UAVs at opposite starting locations interchanging positions. Four different experiments are executed:

- 1) trajectory planning with the method proposed in [25],
- 2) trajectory planning utilizing *RRT-MC*,
- 3) trajectory planning utilizing *BBC-MC*,
- 4) trajectory planning utilizing *CDP-MC*.

For all experiments, d_{\min} is set at a fixed value of 10m. All other parameters are set as follows: sampling time $\delta T = 0.5\text{s}$, UAV mass $m = 300\text{kg}$, with $f_{\text{MAX}} = 1000\text{N}$ and $\Delta f = 300\text{N}$, the maximum achievable speed is $v_{\text{MAX}} = 27\text{m/s}$, the drag coefficient is $\eta = 0.8$, and

Fig. 2: RRT-MC based trajectories for the scenario under consideration (depicted in 3D).

the bounded LOS probability is $2\epsilon = 0.00002$. The noise impacting the UAV motion model is characterized by $\Sigma_\sigma = [0.01 \ 0.01 \ 0.01] \text{m/s}^2$ and the filtering $L_s = d_{\min} + 250\text{m}$, $L_s = d_{\min} + 50\text{m}$ [25] for negative slacks and non-negative slacks experiments, respectively. All UAVs commence simultaneously, employing the following optimization parameters: $CH = 20$ time-steps, $SH = 10$ time-steps, with the update of the controls happening every 5 time-steps.

Fig. 3: CDF of the computation time of all UAVs' generated trajectories.

Fig. 4: CDF of the computation time of all UAVs' generated trajectories for optimization problems just before the UAVs cross each other.

B. Results Without Negative Slacks

A comparison is initially performed between the *RRT-MC* and *BBC-MC* methods versus the initial framework in [25],

Fig. 5: CDF of the pairwise distance of all calculated paths for the scenario under consideration.

Fig. 6: CDF of flying time of all UAVs.

analyzing the UAVs’ flight durations to reach their destinations, their pairwise distance, and most importantly the computation time. The corresponding outcomes are illustrated in Figs. 3-6. Clearly, both *RRT-MC* and *BBC-MC* approaches notably reduce the system’s computation time, generating 97% of the routes in less than 2.5s (i.e., the control update period), thus enabling the framework to be applied in an online fashion (even when using standard computing hardware). Compared to the *MC-SV* method (generating 82% of the routes in less than 2.5s), there is a significant increase; however, these conservative formulations come with the cost of increased flying time (mostly due to the last 2 UAVs that encounter “enlarged” single obstacles (due to clustering), resulting in prolonging their flight times while trying to avoid the obstacles). Concerning LOS, the *RRT-MC* and *BBC-MC* implementations ensure safe trajectories (as indicated by the pairwise distance between UAVs). Additionally, UAVs actively evade congested environments with less complexity by exploiting spatio-temporal data. However, as previously pointed out, increased deviation from the optimal route directly correlates with extended flight times, revealing the trade-off between computation times versus flight duration.

C. Results With Negative Slacks

The integration of negative slack variables into trajectory planning (with λ taking values $\in [-30, 0]$) emphasizes a more cautious approach, prioritizing increased separation distances between UAVs. Indeed, Fig. 7 illustrates that when the clustering approaches are utilized, in conjunction with the negative slacks, the measured minimum distance is now approximately 20m (in contrast to the 10m reported for the *MC-SV* method). However, trying to uphold increased

spatial margins among the vehicles has as a trade-off the probability of extended flight durations (Fig. 8), mainly due to the fact that at some point UAVs encounter “enlarged” single obstacles (due now both to clustering and the effects of the negative slacks). The delicate balance between careful planning and prolonged flight times underscores the intricate interplay between ensuring safety and achieving operational efficiency in the implementation of trajectories. Setting negative λ values increases the safety distance but also increases computational complexity, since additional constraints are introduced over the feasible solution space (see Figs. 9-10). As expected, this computational complexity can be reduced when *RRT-MC* and *BBC-MC* clustering techniques are used, instead of the *MC-SV* approach (Figs. 9-10).

The experimental results clearly support the high performance of the proposed method, confirming its effectiveness and highlighting its potential for practical application in real-world scenarios.

Fig. 7: CDF of the pairwise distance of all calculated paths ($\lambda \in [-30, 0]$).

Fig. 8: CDF of flying time of all UAVs ($\lambda \in [-30, 0]$).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This work formulates an optimization framework for UAM trajectory planning, focusing on safe trajectories, while considering uncertainties in the predicted future system states of UAVs. The optimization formulation addresses the challenges posed by dense scenarios. Initially, it transforms safety concave constraints into manageable piecewise linear constraints. Subsequently, it employs a receding horizon approach to periodically recalculate UAV trajectories, ensuring that UAV LOS probability remains below a predefined threshold. Additionally, two different clustering strategies

Fig. 9: CDF of the computation time of all UAVs' generated trajectories ($\lambda \in [-30, 0]$).

Fig. 10: CDF of the computation time of all UAVs' generated trajectories for optimization problems just before the UAVs cross each other ($\lambda \in [-30, 0]$).

RRT-MC and *BBC-MC* are devised for clustering nearby UAVs and encapsulating them into a single polyhedron per cluster. Moreover, it introduces a *CDP-MC* (negative slacks) method to effectively disperse UAVs, thereby alleviating congestion within the 3D environment. All proposed frameworks retain in their formulation the piecewise linear constraints and their 4D properties, while reducing complexity, in an effort to ensure real-time applicability.

A comprehensive set of experiments is conducted to explore the performance of the proposed frameworks and showcase their applicability in dense environments. The results of the proposed clustering methods show promising results in terms of real-time computation times while maintaining safe trajectories. However, there is a clear trade-off between computation times and flight duration, as the trajectories deviate from their optimal routes, resulting in increased flight times. Further, the experimental results on the behavior of the *CDP-MC* approach with negative slack variables showcase the increase in the pairwise distance between UAVs. Nevertheless, it is evident that there exists a trade-off between the values of the negative slacks and the computational time, flying time, and pairwise distance.

Future work involves implementing ML-based techniques for planning safe UAV trajectories in real-time, as well as the hardware/software implementation of the proposed techniques for real-world experimentation.

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